

ROLE OF LEADERSHIP STYLE IN TEACHING PROCESS

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses the nature of leadership and its important role in the educational process. The purpose of the scientific article is to reveal the theoretical analysis of leadership and its positive results in practice.

Key words: *leadership style, trust, self-confidence, human development, teaching process, pedagogy, high standards , high-performance*

Introduction

"Leadership means never forgetting the why, the ethics of the purpose, and all those people—teachers and students—who have put their trust in you," said one leader. "Leadership is never believing your own press." Leigh Patel (2018) stated that a modest stewardship of learning is the first and most important quality of educational leadership. We have plenty of highly compensated leaders in education right now, but they tend to talk more about innovation than learning and even less about the patterns of denied access to education at the population level. Leadership in education must be able to acknowledge the legacies and flaws of individualistic, Eurocentric frameworks of human development that exist for the sake of success and dominance.

To quote Ken Lindblom Leadership in education entails continuously keeping the pupils' learning as the only objective. An education leader will always stay focused on the right things if they keep that at the forefront of their minds.

Methodology

It entails being current with organizational theory, content theory, and instructional theory. It refers to inspiring and instructing. It entails resisting disruptive, even hostile, external pressures and encouraging societal change that will improve learning for all kids. It entails promoting student learning both internally and externally.

It entails doing all possible to make sure that every student has everything they require) in order to learn as well as possible. It entails supplying a professional environment that enables—and obliges—teachers to carry out the actions they believe are best for students' learning, including the freedom to disregard anything that might get in the way of that learning, if necessary.

The "bottom line" in education is student learning, yet standardized tests don't accurately reflect student learning sufficiently to serve as independent dependable assessments.

Data collection and Analysis

Good educational leadership is important because schools constantly seek to enhance their operations and give students the best education possible. Surprisingly, a large number of individuals participating in their community's educational system are unsure of what constitutes educational leadership. Education leadership is a process that combines the efforts, skills, and expertise of educators, parents, and educators with the aim of enhancing not only the standard of instruction but also the educational system as a whole.

The major goal of educational leadership is to ensure academic success through improvements to procedures, instruction, and resources. Unfortunately, without the assistance and cooperation of all parties concerned, including the children, parents, instructors, decision-makers, and even the broader public, this achievement cannot be ensured or even achieved. Educational leadership is a way of quality actually works:

- establish a goal of achieving academic success for all children, regardless of socioeconomic status;
- strive to keep a responsive, safe, and healthy learning environment;
- assign accountability to everyone and enhance the curriculum and teaching strategies.

A strong teaching culture can be developed with the help of leadership in education. It may also affect how well students learn and perform. Effective leadership is widely seen as the foundation for significant changes in education.

Leaders must have a thorough understanding of pedagogy and engage in practice themselves in this effort to enhance learning within the school community. This collaborative leadership approach puts the ego to one side and prioritizes others' needs over one's own. A great leader "must first serve others and that this simple fact is key to his or her greatness: true leadership arises from people whose first motive is a desire to help others," according to the servant leadership school of thought. Servant leaders in education uphold high standards while also assisting teachers and students in developing their abilities to achieve better. These leaders foster a desire for improvement while keeping an eye on both relationships and results. The ten traits of servant leaders, according to the previous president of the Robert K. Greenleaf Center for Servant Leadership, are: listening, empathy, healing, awareness, persuasion, conceptualization, foresight, stewardship, commitment to the growth of others, and fostering community. By removing obstacles, offering resources, and facilitating communication with the entire school community, servant leaders can develop high-performance teachers.

Result and Discussion

People frequently use leadership philosophies that are derived from their genetic makeup, personality, and social environments. This is not a bad thing; part of being a strong leader is understanding which leadership style naturally works the best for you. It's essential to establish a pliable style that incorporates many leadership strategies and

can be adjusted to new situations as they arise in order to increase leadership effectiveness. Authoritarian leaders, often known as autocrats, construct a distinct vision of the final result and how to get there. They establish precise standards and unambiguous expectations. These leaders typically anticipate that their followers would follow their directives without question and without delay. Autocratic leaders don't always think of themselves as "know-it-alls" who are superior to others. In fact, they frequently have a laser-like focus on attaining effective outcomes by predetermined activities that they feel are best for the company. Sometimes an authoritarian leader would consult a small circle of trusted peers before making a decision.

Conclusion

A growing amount of research demonstrates that teaching with instructional leadership do better than others. By enhancing teaching quality, this coaching leadership approach focuses on student learning outcomes. Planning, evaluating, coordinating, and improving teaching and learning are all practices of instructional leadership. Instructional leaders work closely with teachers to assess their performance and support their professional development through coaching and mentoring. To become an instructional leader, one must invest time in pedagogical problem-solving, take steps to enhance instructors' instruction, and hold teachers responsible for developing their instructional abilities. Great teaching processes are built on strong school leadership. According to the evidence, strong leadership is necessary to foster a climate in which every student can receive a high-quality education. Teachers who seek leadership in postgraduate education will be able to support successful teaching and learning practices, keep up with changes in the education sector, and introduce fresh ideas into classrooms. Everyone is aware of the importance of effective leadership for corporate success.

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